

Online Subjective Wellbeing Scale

This is a 14-item scale measuring 2 constructs: Positive affect (7 items) and Negative affect (7 items); these are presented in a random order.

Please think about your online experience during the past four (4) weeks. Then report how much you experienced each of the following feelings, using the scale below.

- 1 = Very rarely or never
- 2 = Rarely
- 3 = Sometimes
- 4 = Often
- 5 = Very often or always

Positive affect:

- Empowered (Pos1)
- Pleased (Pos2)
- Creative (Pos3)
- In Control (Pos4)
- Calm (Pos5)
- Safe (Pos6)
- Happy (Pos7)

Negative affect

- Annoyed (Neg1)
- Anxious (Neg2)
- Apathetic (Neg3)
- Powerless (Neg4)
- Paranoid (Neg5)
- Disempowered (Neg6)
- Sad (Neg7)

Scoring for each subscale is done by totalling the score and dividing by 5 to form a mean of all items.

This scale has been validated using the Rasch method (paper in submission).

The development and use of previous versions has also been reported in:

Dowthwaite, L., Perez Vallejos, E., Creswick, H., Portillo, V., Patel, M., & Zhao, J. (2020). Developing a measure of online wellbeing and user trust. In M. Arias-Olivai, J. Pelegrin-Borondo, K. Murata, & A. M. L. Palma (Eds.), *Societal Challenges in the Smart Society* (pp. 21–33). Universidad de La Rioja.

Dowthwaite, L., Vallejos, E. P., Portillo, V., Patel, M., Zhao, J., & Creswick, H. (2023). An Exploration of how Trust Online Relates to Psychological and Subjective Wellbeing. Proceedings of the First International Symposium on Trustworthy Autonomous Systems. TAS'23, Edinburgh.
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